

TEXTURE SHARP TRANSITION MECHANISM OF PYROCARBON BASED ON MONTE CARLO

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1 General Introduction

Carbon/carbon composites are the most promising high-temperature Structural material which can be used widely in both aeronautic and aerospace industries [1]. Isothermal, isobaric chemical vapor infiltration (I-CVI) is widely used to density porous carbon performs, and the microstructure of the deposited pyrocarbon matrix can be various by controlling the process parameters. These texture differences should influence the mechanical properties of CVI-materials [2]. A large number of polarizing microscopes show that different texture transition is sharp, especially between medium texture (MT) and high texture (HT) [3].

The aim of the present work is to set up a kinetic heterogeneous reaction model based on the Langmuir-Hinshelwood (L-H) mechanism and the Particle-Filler (P-F) conceptual model [4] to study the sharp transition of MT/HT.

2 Model and Results

2.1 Model Set-up

As shown in Fig.1, the multistep heterogeneous reaction kinetic model formulates both the pyrocarbon deposition process and the texture formation process based on L-H mechanism and the P-F conceptual model. Adsorption, desorption and dehydrogenation reactions are involved in the kinetic model, and moreover MT and HT pyrocarbons are clearly differentiated as two metastable species of carbon. The unimolecular dehydrogenation reactions of either light linear hydrocarbons being fillers (C_2) or light aromatic species being Particles (C_6) result in the formation of MT, while the bimolecular dehydrogenation reaction between P and F species leads to the formation of HT.

In the model, we assume the precursor R is already completely converted into species C_2 and C_6 on the substrate surface or at the entrance of pores, so that

$[R]=0$, and $k_8=0$. In MC simulations, the surface of substrate is represented by a two-dimensional square lattice of $N \times N$ sites ($N=50$) with periodic boundary conditions. C_2 adsorption, desorption and deposition occur on an empty site while C_6 can only occur on three nearest-neighbor empty sites.

2.2 Results

As shown in Fig.2, at the lower value of $a=0.1$ (a is proportional to the initial concentration of C_2), the surface coverage of C_2 has a sharp transition region. As the increase of a , two steady-state branches can be observed: below R_0 (the transition point between this two branches), the surface of substrate is mainly occupied by C_2 ; above R_0 , the surface of substrate is mainly occupied by C_2 and C_6 , and the formation of clusters of both species surrounded by empty sites can observe (Fig.3b).

By further calculations, we find that while $R < R_0$, the mainly events happened in the surface of substrate are C_2 absorption, desorption and dehydrogenation reactions (MT deposition mechanism) when the surface has achieved steady-state; While $R > R_0$, the mainly events happened in the surface of substrate are C_2 absorption, C_6 absorption and surface bimolecular reaction (HT deposition mechanism). So MT is formed at the condition of $R < R_0$, while HT is formed at the condition of $R > R_0$.

3 Conclusion

R is an important factor to the deposition of pyrocarbon which control the deposition mechanism: MT is formed at the condition of $R < R_0$, while HT is formed at the condition of $R > R_0$. So while R is near R_0 , if some system parameter (eg. T) has a small oscillation, it is possible to break the local equilibrium of the system, leading to the sharp transition from HT to MT or MT to HT.

In our model, there are a lot of approximations for the convenience of calculation, so all the results we

got are qualitative. In the future, a more detailed and quantitative model will be used to investigate the texture transition of pyrocarbon during the process of CVD/CVI.

Fig.1. Heterogeneous surface reaction mechanism proposed for pyrolytic carbon deposition and texture formation

species, empty sites are left white), Notice the formation of clusters of both species surrounded by empty sites, (a) $R=11.6$ (b) $R=11.8$

References

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Fig.2. Surface coverage of C_2 as a function of $R=[C_6]/[C_2]$ at various a .

Fig.3. Snapshot configuration of the substrate surface while the system achieved steady-state around R_0 (~ 11.7) when $a=0.5$ ($\times C_2$ -species, $\bullet C_6$ -